

METHODS FOR DEVELOPING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS

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Annotation: This article presents various methods for developing English speaking skills. It also describes in detail the communicative approach, the audio-lingual method, the immersion method and other effective techniques. The article provides recommendations on self-study of English, selection of educational materials and organization of classes. The purpose of the article is to help English language learners develop oral speech and achieve a confident level of language proficiency.

Key words: Methods for developing English speaking skills, communicative approach, audio-lingual method, educational materials, oral speech, skill development, confident language proficiency

There are many methods for developing English speaking skills.

I. Listening Developing listening skills is key to understanding English.

Development of English listening skills:

1. Immersion in the language environment: Listen to English music: Choose songs you like and sing along. Study the lyrics and try to understand their meaning. Watch movies and TV series in English: First, you can use subtitles in Russian, then in English, and then without them. Listen to podcasts and audiobooks: Choose topics that interest you. Use different playback speeds to improve speech comprehension. Communicate with native speakers: Find language partners online or in your city. Attend conversation clubs.

2. Active listening: Don't just listen, but set yourself tasks: Try to get the main idea. Write down the keywords. Answer the questions after listening. Use different listening methods: Pre-listening: look at the title, pictures, questions to make a guess about the content. While listening: try to catch the main idea, key words, answer questions. After listening: repeat what you listened to, answer questions, complete assignments.

3. Development of phonetic skills: Learn transcription: This will help you pronounce words correctly and understand them by ear. Pay attention to intonation: She can change the meaning of what is said. Practice shadow pronunciation. Listen and repeat after the speaker, trying to imitate his intonation and pronunciation.

4. Expansion of vocabulary: Learn new words and expressions: Use word cards, language learning apps. Read adapted literature: This will help you encounter new words in context. Use context: It is not always necessary to know the exact translation of every word in order to understand the meaning of what is being said.

5. Regular exercise: Practice listening every day: Even 15-20 minutes a day will be helpful. Use different resources: Textbooks, websites, applications, YouTube channels. Don't be afraid of mistakes: Mistakes are part of the learning process. Additional tips: Follow your interests: Listen to what interests you, so you will be more motivated. Don't set unrealistic goals: Start with simple materials and gradually move on to more complex ones. Praise yourself for your achievements: This will help you stay motivated. Remember: Developing listening skills is a long process. Don't expect instant results. Be patient and persistent. Using these methods and tips, you can significantly improve your English listening skills.

II. Speaking The development of speaking skills is necessary for cadets to be able to communicate effectively in English. Development of English speaking skills

1. Expansion of vocabulary: Learn new words and phrases every day. Use word cards, apps, dictionaries, and other resources.

Read books and articles in English. Choose topics that interest you to make it easier for you to learn new vocabulary. Listen to English-language podcasts, audiobooks and music. This will help you get used to the sound of the language and improve your pronunciation.

Watch movies and TV series in English. You can turn on subtitles in English to better understand the speech of the characters.

2. Pronunciation practice. Repeat words and phrases after the speaker. Pay attention to intonation, stress and articulation. Record your speech on a voice recorder. This will help you hear your mistakes and improve your pronunciation. Find a language partner to practice speaking. Use online services to check your pronunciation.

3. Development of listening skills: Listen to English spoken as often as possible. This will help you get used to the sound of the language and improve your listening comprehension. Watch movies and TV series in English without subtitles. Listen to English-language podcasts, audiobooks and music. Use listening exercises from textbooks and online resources.

4. Development of speaking skills: Find a language partner to practice speaking. Attend English speaking clubs. Participate in online communities of English speakers. Don't be afraid to speak English, even if you make mistakes.

5. Use of additional resources: Use online resources to learn English such as Duolingo, Memrise, Babbel, italki and others. Sign up for an English language course. Find an English tutor. Remember: Developing English speaking skills takes time and effort. Don't be afraid to make mistakes and keep practicing. Find ways to make learning English interesting and fun. Set realistic goals for yourself and gradually achieve them.

III. Reading The development of reading skills allows cadets to read English-language literature, professional articles and other materials. Methods for developing English reading skills

1. Select materials according to your level: Start with adapted texts where the vocabulary and grammatical structures correspond to your level. Gradually move on to more complex texts, such as news, articles, books, etc.

2. Expand your vocabulary: Use dictionaries and apps to learn words. Write down new words and expressions that you come across in texts. Use new words in your speech and writing.

3. Improve your grammar: Learn basic English grammar rules. Practice grammar exercises. Pay attention to grammatical structures in the texts you read.

4. Develop scanning and keyword identification skills: Learn to quickly find the necessary information in the text. Identify keywords that will help you understand the meaning of the text.

5. Practice reading aloud: This will help you improve your pronunciation and intonation. Read aloud every day, even if you only have a few minutes.

6. Use different reading methods: Silent reading: suitable for quickly familiarizing yourself with the text. Reading aloud: Helps improve pronunciation and intonation. Screening: reading for the purpose of retelling. Annotating: writing down main ideas and keywords from the text.

7. Make reading English texts part of your daily life: Read news, articles, books and other materials in English. Subscribe to English-language blogs and websites. Listen to English-language podcasts and audiobooks.

8. Use online resources: There are many websites and apps that can help you improve your English reading skills. Some of them offer adapted texts, exercises, dictionaries and other tools.

9. Don't be afraid of mistakes: Mistakes are part of the learning process. Don't be afraid to do them, the main thing is to learn from them.

10. Find like-minded people: Chat with people who are also learning English. Discuss the texts you read, share your impressions and advice. Developing English reading skills takes time and effort. Be patient and persistent, and you will eventually achieve your goals. Use a timer to track your reading speed. Set goals for yourself, such as reading a certain number of pages per day. Reward yourself for success.

IV. Letter The development of writing skills is necessary so that cadets can write letters, reports, essays and other texts in English. Methods for developing English writing skills:

1. Reading: Read a lot and often. The more you read, the better you will understand the structure and style of the English language. Choose materials that interest you. This will help you stay motivated and enjoy reading. Pay attention to grammar, punctuation and spelling. Write down unfamiliar words and expressions. Try to retell what you read in your own words.

2. Letter: Write as often as possible. This will help you develop your grammar, punctuation and spelling skills. Start with simple tasks. For example, you can write letters to friends, keep a diary or blog. Gradually move on to more complex tasks. For example, you can write essays, articles, or even stories. Use dictionaries and reference materials. Check your work for errors. Ask friends or a teacher to read your work and give you feedback.

3. Practice: Communicate with native speakers. This will help you improve your writing and speaking skills. Participate in online communities. This will help you get feedback on your work and meet other people who are learning English. Use apps and online resources. The development of English speaking skills among university cadets is a complex and multifaceted process. Don't be afraid to make mistakes. Mistakes are part of the learning process. Be patient. Developing writing skills takes time and effort. Do not give up. Persistence and determination will help you achieve success. Developing language skills is a long-term process. There is no universal method. Find methods that work for you. Be motivated and goal-oriented.

References:

1. Azimov, E. G. Theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. – M.: Publishing House "Inostranka", 2009.
2. Bim, I. L. Pedagogical grammar. – M.: "Russian language", 2008.

3. Passov, E.I. Communicative method of teaching foreign language speaking. – M.: “Enlightenment”, 2008.
4. Khaleeva, I. L. Theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. – M.: “Higher School”, 2009.